

Drought Hazard Assessment and Mapping in Upper Seonath Sub-Basin Using GIS

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Abstract— Drought is a natural anomaly experienced when circulation pattern get blocked in one phase, or push outside their normal residence time of variation. The assessment of drought impact on agricultural land in Upper Seonath Sub-basin is essential for making mitigation plan to reduce the impact of drought. The study has been conducted in Upper Seonath sub basin of Chhattisgarh State, having total geographical area of 7292 sq.km out of which 62.16% is occupied by agricultural land. Agricultural droughts can occur due to number of reasons, including low precipitation, the timing of water availability or decreased access to water supplies. The Standardized precipitation index is probability based, designed as spatially invariant indicator of drought that recognizes the importance of time scales in the analysis of water availability and water use (Nathaniel B. Gutman, 1999). A drought assessment model based on SPI in GIS environment is used in the present study. The study carried out for 22 stations dataset in 31-year time scale. The aim of the present study is the determination of natural anomaly in a time period of 1983–2013 by using SPI. Drought hazard mapping is done for 31-year time period based on panoramic station points data using geo-statistical analysis of ArcGIS. Zonal statistics derivation of drought hazard map is done based on implementation borders of blocks.

Keywords— Drought hazard, GIS, Hydrological cycle, SPI.

I. INTRODUCTION

Drought is explained as the unusual low level of precipitation over a certain period as meteorological drought. The shortage of water propagates through the hydrological cycle and combines with high evaporation, the insufficient moisture in the topsoil may cause an agricultural drought and subsequently a hydrological drought may develop when groundwater and streamflow are reduced. The different types of drought are significantly influenced by each other through the natural hydrological cycle (Tallaksen and Van Lanen, 2003). The year's rainfall is concentrated in the monsoon season (June–September) contributes about 75–90% of the total annual rainfall, small changes in the location or timing of precipitation can have a big regional impact on agriculture.

The exact position and timing of monsoons are influenced by many factors and would vary from year to year. Precipitation is highly specific to a region as average precipitation may vary considerably spatially hence agricultural drought may also developed due to the inability to access water when needed rather than from the lack of water itself. Drought is unpredictable, while its recurrence is recognizable. The drought occurrence frequency and drought-affected area are still increasing. Therefore, drought hazards assessment is essential for making mitigation plans to reduce the impact of drought. GIS technique is applied to demonstrate the impacts of drought hazard on agricultural productions through spatial distribution of climatic data.

II. STANDARDIZED PRECIPITATION INDEX

The SPI is a tool developed by McKee et al., 1993 for the purpose of defining and monitoring local droughts. SPI is value added information related to cumulative effects of a prolonged and abnormal moisture deficiency based on statistical computation. SPI expressed by a numeric number. It is based on equiprobability transformation of aggregated monthly precipitation into a standard normal variable. SPI has advantages of statistical consistency and the ability to describe both short-term and long-term drought impacts through the different time scales of precipitation anomalies. These various time scales can be useful in assessing effects on different components of the hydrologic system. The SPI calculation is based on two assumptions first is the variability of precipitation is much higher than that of other variables, such as temperature, potential evapotranspiration (PET) and the other variables are stationary. SPI having some limitations also that it relies on one input that is precipitation. There should be no missing data in the time series and the record length is required to be at least 30 years. McKee used the classification system shown in Table 1 to define dry and wet events.

TABLE I
Drought classification based on SPI

SPI Value	Class
> 2	Extremely Wet (EW)
1.5 to 1.99	Very Wet (SW)
1.0 to 1.49	Moderately Wet (MW)
-0.99 to +0.99	Near Normal (NN)
-1.0 to -1.49	Moderately Dry (MD)
-1.5 to -1.99	Very Dry (SD)
< -2.0	Extremely Dry (ED)

III. STUDY AREA

The area selected for the study is the Upper Seonath sub-basin which is Sub-basin of Mahanadi River. The Seonath River is major tributary of Mahanadi River, is a non-perennial river. The basin of Seonath located between 20°16' N to 22°41' N latitude and 80°25' E to 82°35' E longitude. Total geographical area of Upper Seonath sub basin is 7292 sq.km. The two districts of Chhattisgarh State namely Durg and Rajnandgaon are covered in this basin. The southwest monsoon sets over this region during the second week of June and rainfall activity continuous till second week of October. The mean annual rainfall in the basin varies from 1005 mm to 1255 mm. Figure 1 shows the location map of the study area.

Figure 1. Location map of Upper Seonath sub basin

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted for this study is begins with the delineation of Upper Seonath Sub-basin boundary. The delineated Upper Seonath Sub-basin DEM serves as the base template for the drought severity map generation. Time series of drought indices is used as input in ArcGIS to depict the spatial variation of drought event in Upper Seonath Sub-basin. SPI is computed by equiprobability transformation of aggregated monthly precipitation gamma distribution into a corresponding standard normal quantile as the SPI. SPI represents a z-score, or the number of standard deviation above or below that on event is from the mean. This computed SPI value fed into ArcGIS software with its location and interpolating with the help of special analyst tool. The obtained thematic maps are then reclassified according to the event in two classes by assigning the negative value to weight 1 as drought event and positive value to weight 0 as normal condition. Similarly the entire maps are again reclassified into two classes by assigning the positive value to weight 1 as flood event and negative value to weight 0 as normal condition (Table 2). The obtained 31 reclassified dry and wet event themes are then sum overlaying in the raster data model using the weight values of the thematic maps respectively obtained themes are drought hazard and flood hazard maps. To identify drought susceptible area relative analysis of drought hazard and flood hazard maps in raster calculator is done. The working methodology is graphically represented in Figure 2. The obtained drought themes are depicted in Figure 3. To measure the natural anomaly risk, hazard index computed which focuses on the probability of crop failure combined with the degree of rainfall variability. Low drought hazard index indicates relatively low chances of crop failure, and High indicates an increased probability of crop failure, due mainly to rainfall variability. Hazard index produced by sum overlaying of the drought thematic maps and flood thematic maps, for a time period of 30 years. This hazard index integrates the annual drought theme and flood theme severity for assigned hazard occurrences in the long-term time period shown in Figure 4. This map is applicable when divided into legal and formal implementation zones. After the zonal statistics of ArcGIS extensions, the drought hazard index map was produced based on 15 block polygons of Upper Seonath Sub-basin as in Figure 5. In this map, the mean event and probability of drought occurrences assigned to categorize DHI over a 31-year time period from 1983 to 2013 in Table 3. The DHI map was categorized into four levels of low, moderate, high, and very high.

Figure 2. Procedural flow chart of Methodology

TABLE II
Weights and Themes Assigned to Hazard Category and SPI Values

SPI Value	Category	Drought Hazard		Flood Hazard	
		Weight	Theme	Weight	Theme
$\geq +2$ to -1.0	Extreme wet to near normal	0	Near normal	1	Severe flood
-0.99 to ≤ -2.0	Moderate to extreme dry	1	Severe drought	0	Near normal

Figure 3. Annual drought thematic maps for 30 year time period

V. RESULT

SPI computation has been applied to long-term precipitation data at 22 stations for the period 1983-2013 (January 1983 to December 2013). Four representative stations namely Dongargaon, Madiyan, Bhanupratappur, Ambagarh were selected to show SPI value in the very high, high, moderate, low drought susceptible areas those are located in central, west, south and east of sub-basin, respectively and the bar plot of yearly SPI for above station is shown in Figure 7.

On the basis of DHI the entire sub-basin were categorized into four classes of very high, high, moderate and low drought susceptible area. It is revealed from the analysis that only one block of the sub-basin having 7.1% of total geographical area is susceptible to very low probability whereas 21.5% and 55.4% of total geographical area consisting of five blocks each are having moderate and high chances of drought. 16% of the area of sub-basin is found to have very high susceptibility of drought consisting of four blocks, graphically presented in Figure 6. According to drought severity classification as shown in Table 1, the number of events from extreme dry to extreme wet for the 22 station is shown in Table 4, it was found that in about 14.8 years are near normal. There was moderate dry condition in 2.16 years and 1.54 years were sever dry in one complete hydrological cycle of 31 year. The occurrences of normal, wet, moderate, sever and extreme dry years were then counted and expressed as a percentage from the total number of years. Figure 8 depicts the distribution of normal, wet, moderate, sever and extreme dry years for the time period of 1983-2013.

Figure 4. Drought hazard occurrences based on SPI for 31 year time scale

TABLE III
Mean Event and Probability of Drought Occurrences Assigned to Categorize Drought Hazard Index (DHI) In 31 years Time Period

Drought hazard index	Drought occurrences	
	Mean event	Probability (%)
Low	> 2	10-20%
Moderate	2 – 4	20-30%
High	4 – 8	30-40%
Very High	8 – 12	40-50%

Figure 5. Hazard zones of Upper Seonath sub-basin

According to results mitigation measures are necessary to provide in this area. The outcome of the study can be used as a guide for proper utilization of the reservoir during drought and will be helpful in planning, development and management of drought mitigation measures, due to temporal and spatial non-uniform rainfall distribution and varying water demand in the sub-basin. Drought impact can be reduced by implementing the ability of water regulation throughout the rainy and dry seasons. It seems that our study provided a scientific basis for further research of agricultural drought hazard in distinguished major hazard zones in sub-basin.

Figure 6. Spatial extent of drought

VI. CONCLUSION

The aim of this study is to assess the drought vulnerability in the upper Seonath sub basin. The produced zonal hazard index map was categorized into four levels of low, moderate, high, and very high, which demonstrated the probability of drought occurrences of 10–20 %, 20–30 %, 30–40 % and 40–50 % respectively. It revealed from the study that Upper Seonath Sub Basin subjected to maximum dry condition in 17% time of the hydrological cycle, which corresponds to extreme dry condition at 5.88%, severe dry condition at 35.29% and moderate dry condition at 58.82% time of drought event respectively.

Figure 8. Distribution of dry, normal and wet event

TABLE IV
Drought Severity Classification from extremely dry to extremely wet for panoramic 22 stations

Stations	Admabad	Ambagarh	Balod	Bhanu_pur	Bhatagaon	Bhilai	Dhamdha	Dong_gon	Dong_grh	Doundi	DoundiL	Durg	Gondly	Gunderdehi	Gurur	Khapri	Kharkhara	Madiyan	Mohala	Patan	Selud	Seo-sigdai
EW	0	2	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	3	0	1	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0	0
SW	0	0	1	4	1	0	1	0	1	3	0	1	1	0	3	0	0	1	4	2	2	0
MW	8	3	3	1	4	0	2	0	3	3	1	2	4	6	0	2	1	3	3	3	4	6
NN	19	23	22	20	21	24	22	22	20	20	23	19	18	18	24	23	25	23	19	20	19	15
MD	1	1	3	4	3	1	2	7	4	3	4	5	3	4	0	2	1	0	3	4	4	8
SD	3	1	1	1	0	5	3	0	2	2	0	3	3	3	4	2	1	2	2	2	0	2
ED	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0

Figure 7. SPI values for annual rainfall for the four representatives station in each DHI category

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